

STRUCTURAL OPTIMIZATION TO PREVENT CRACK PROPAGATION FOR CFRP CRYOGENIC TANK

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we conducted structural optimization for CFRP cryogenic propellant-tank. Propellant tank accounts for large proportion of the structural weight in the space transportation system. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are superior in specific strength and specific stiffness. Therefore it is possible to reduce the structural weight of the tank by applying CFRP. In cryogenic temperature, the difference of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) causes large thermal stress and crack might occur. In this study, optimizations were performed by genetic algorithm and we calculated energy release rate by virtual crack closure technics. In the finite element method, we considered two types of deformation: when merely the temperature of tank was decreased and when the pressure was applied to the tank in the decreased temperature. We conducted two types of optimizations in this study. One is liner wall thickness optimization. By this optimization, notch-like shape was generated near the cap and we found that energy release rate reduced. Another optimization is curved wall-shape optimization. By this optimization, shape having a step near the cap was created and reduction of energy release rate occurred. Based on the above results of optimizations, we concluded that if suitable position and dome shape are determined, this structure can prevent crack propagation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the future reusable space transportation system such as space plane, saving of structural weight is essential. The propellant tank that is used for reusable space transportation system occupies most of the structure weight. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have very high specific stiffness and specific strength. Therefore application of CFRP to propellant tank can significantly reduce structural weight [1-3]. The tank stores cryogenic liquid propellant such as liquid oxygen and hydrogen. For this reason the tank must sustain at such temperature. The tank is usually made by a combination of metal materials and CFRP. Between CFRP and metallic material, there is large difference of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). At cryogenic temperature, it causes extensive thermal stress and may lead fractures near the cap of tank. In this study, we conducted four optimizations about structure of tank, liner thickness and curved shape of dome part, to prevent propagation of crack by using genetic algorithm. After that we propose a new design of the cryogenic tank based on the results of optimizations. Proposed design of tank was proven that it efficiently prevents crack propagation.

The present paper is organized as follows. After the introduction, the methods to obtain energy release rate are explained in section 2. We define the tank shape and maximum expected operating

pressure (MEOP) in section 3. We describe details of optimizations in section 4, and their result in section 5. Conclusions from the present study are drawn in the last section.

2 METHODS TO OBTAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE USING VCCT

In this study, in order to calculate energy release rate, we employed the virtual crack closure technique (standard VCCT) [4]. The energy release rate G under constant loading condition can be calculated as,

$$G = \frac{\partial U}{\partial A} \quad (1)$$

where U and A denote strain energy and area of crack propagation, respectively. Equation (1) means that energy release rate is equal to change of elastic energy when small crack propagation occurred. In this study, we consider a crack in elastic media. The change of elastic energy between the state of before crack propagation (Fig.1 (a)) and the state of after crack propagation (Fig.1 (b)) is equal to the work of the external force $f (= (f_x, f_y, f_z))$ that closes the crack. Then the work for closing crack ΔW is expressed as,

$$\Delta W = \int_{\Delta A} \int_0^{u_i^{a+\Delta a}} f_i du_i dA \quad (2)$$

where $u_i^{a+\Delta a}$ represents relative displacement of upper and lower surfaces of crack. Because it is equal to the change of elastic energy ΔU , energy release rate under constant loading is expressed as,

$$G = \frac{\partial W}{\partial A} \quad (3)$$

Then we apply it to finite element method. When we assume that f_i is nodal force and displacement δ_i is relative displacement at adjacent node P, the energy release rate G is represented as,

$$G = \frac{\Delta W}{\Delta A} = \frac{1}{2\Delta A} \sum f_i \delta_i \quad (4)$$

where the nodes to calculate relative displacement δ_i is deferent from the node to calculate nodal force (see figure 2). In the standard VCCT method, it is assumed that when the node Q, which calculate nodal force, is divided into two nodes, the crack opening displacement at Q will be equal to that of the node P before separation of node Q.

However in the simulation for structures that have curved surface, these two displacements might be different from each other. In such case, it is desirable to use the same nodes for measuring crack opening displacement and measuring nodal force [4]. We called this method two-step VCCT approach. In this method, finite element analyses are performed twice: before crack opening and after crack opening, and nodal force and relative displacement are calculated at the same node. In this method, it is unnecessary to assume similarity of crack, because energy release rate is calculated from two conditions. While computational cost of this method is simply twice as much as that of standard VCCT. In this study, we used standard VCCT in optimizations and parametric studies because we have to perform a lot of simulations for optimizations. However, we confirmed whether standard VCCT was applicable before optimizations.

Figure 1 Distribution of stress and displacement around crack tip.

Figure 2 Nodal force and relative displacement in elements.

Figure 3 Schematic of two-step VCCT.

3 CONFIGURATION OF CFRP CRYOGENIC TANK

In this study, we conducted two types of optimizations: optimization of liner thickness and that of curved shape of dome part. It is assumed that the tank is used at $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and maximum expected operating pressure (MEOP) is 5 MPa. We set the diameter of cylinder part to 1 m and the diameter of cap to 0.2 m. Aluminum alloy (A6061) is utilized as liner, and it is wrapped by CFRP. We set the thickness of CFRP so that burst pressure became 10 MPa. We considered the turnaround of prepreg tape in the cap region. It was assumed that CFRP was wound by only helical winding at the dome part, whereas at the cylindrical part, CFRP was composed by two layers: helical and hoop layers. Figure 4 shows the schematic view of tank. In this study, the purpose of optimization is to obtain the shape to prevent propagation of crack near the cap. Therefore FEM analyses were merely conducted for the dome part. However, in order to consider the effect of the cylinder part, short cylinder was attached at the root of the dome. FEM analyses were conducted in two conditions. In one condition, the tank was cooled down to $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ from $120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is the temperature of CFRP/Al liner bonding, and the temperature was regarded as stress free temperature. In this study, the value of objective function of this condition is called as 'Cooling'. In another condition, we applied the internal pressure of 5 MPa, which is equal to MEOP to the tank model in after cooling. The value of objective function of this condition is called as 'Pressure'. In this study, we conducted each type of optimizations: liner

thickness and curved shape of the dome part, under each condition: Cooling and Pressure. Therefore, we conducted four optimizations in total. In FEM analyses, we utilized axisymmetric solid elements, CGAX4R and CGAX3 in Abaqus/Standard. At helical layer, we defined the winding angle α of fiber based on geodesic curve as shown in equation (5).

$$\sin \alpha = r_0 / r \tag{5}$$

where r_0 and r represent the radius of cap and the dome portion at a certain position, respectively. We set the fracture criterion as shown in equation (6).

$$f = \left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} \right)^m + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} \right)^m \tag{6}$$

where G_I and G_{II} represent mode I and mode II energy release rate, and G_{IC} and G_{IIC} represent mode I and mode II fracture toughness respectively. We employed the power law as fracture criterion. We decided the multiplier of criterion, G_{IC} and G_{IIC} based on MMB, DCB, and ENF tests at cryogenic temperature [5-9]. In this study, we used $G_{IC} = 1.3 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, $G_{IIC} = 1.0 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, and $m = 1$. If f becomes larger than 1, crack propagation occurs. We conducted VCCT analysis for the structure that configuration is described above. The structure, which is called isotensoid, was designed by the netting theory. Tables 1 and 2 show the material properties of CFRP and Al alloy. In this analysis, we set initial crack length to 5 mm from the cap. Figure 5 shows the result of this analysis. From this analysis, the values of fracture criterion are more than 1 and it indicates crack propagate in both conditions.

Figure 4 Schematic view of CFRP cryogenic tank.

Figure 5 Initial value of fracture criterion f

Temperature	23 °C	-196 °C
Longitudinal modulus E_1	159.6 GPa	161.3 GPa
Transverse modulus $E_2 (= E_3)$	8.73 GPa	12.67 GPa
Longitudinal shear modulus $G_{12} (= G_{13})$	4.51 GPa	7.18 GPa
Transverse shear modulus G_{23}	3.01 GPa	4.37 GPa
Major Poisson's ratio $\nu_{12} (= \nu_{13})$	0.328	0.328
Transverse Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	0.45	0.45
Longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion α_1	-6.62×10^{-9}	-3.18×10^{-8}
Transverse coefficient of thermal expansion α_2 ($=\alpha_3$)	3.70×10^{-5}	3.10×10^{-5}

Table 1 Material properties of unidirectional CFRP

Temperature	23	-196
Young's modulus E	70.9GPa	77.1GPa
Poisson's ratio ν	0.33	0.35
Coefficient of thermal expansion α	2.10×10^{-5}	1.68×10^{-5}

Table 2 Material properties of aluminum alloy

4 OPTIMIZATIONS

4.1 Optimization method

We employed genetic algorithm, which can perform probabilistic search, for optimizations. In first generation, individuals were generated in a range of design values randomly. We used the elite preservation strategy, which is the method to select superior individuals for next generation. We stopped optimizations when the number of generation became 200. Flowchart of the optimization is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 Flowchart of method of optimization, where FEM model is created by Abaqus / CAE and VCCT analysis is carried out in Abaqus / standard.

4.2 Optimization for liner thickness

We conducted optimization for liner thickness. We used isotensoid in curved shape and set the design variables as shown in Fig. 7 Thickness of each point, which is indicated by dotted line in Fig. 7 was design variable. Design variables were placed every 10 mm in the region where distance from the cap is smaller than 60 mm. We also placed a design variable at the point where the distance from the cap is 93 mm in order to connect smoothly with the other region. Thickness of the region where the distance from the cap is larger than 93 mm was set to 2 mm. The upper limit of the design variables was set to 9 mm, because the height of the cap was 18 mm. We used the half value of the cap height for the upper limit. The lower limit of the design variables was set to 2 mm due to limit of the manufacture. Objective function and the range of design variables are shown in Eq. (7), and we used Eq. (8) for calculation of fitness.

$$\begin{cases} \text{minimize } f(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} \\ 2 \leq x_i \leq 9 \\ \Delta x_i = 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$fitness = 1/(1 + f(\mathbf{x})) \quad (8)$$

Figure 7 Optimization points of liner thickness.

4.3 Optimization for curved surface shape

We conducted optimization for curved surface shape. The thickness of the liner near the cap was fixed in this optimization. We defined the curved surface shape as shown in Fig. 8. We used isotenoid to define the initial value R_i . Angles θ_i in Fig. 8 were fixed, and parameters r_i were subtracted from R_i . Curved surface shape R'_i was calculated as $R_i - r_i$. Design points, which constitute the dorm part, were 44 points in this optimization. We used 20 parameters r near the cap and position of the cap d as design variables (see Fig.8). Therefore there were 21 design variables in this optimization. The upper and lower limits were set due to consideration of computational cost. Objective function and range of design variables are shown in Eq. (9), and we used Eq. (8) to calculate fitness.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{minimize } f(\mathbf{r}, d) = \frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} \\ -0.63 \leq r_i \leq 0.64 \\ \Delta r_i = 0.01 \\ -6.3 \leq d \leq 6.4 \\ \Delta d = 0.1 \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

Figure 8 Schematic view of change in the dome shape where the dashed line represents Isotenoid and the solid line represents curved surface obtained by GA.

5 RESULTS OF OPTIMIZATIONS

5.1 Results of optimization for liner thickness

The results of liner thickness optimization are shown in Figs. 9 and 10. In Fig 9, the shapes after optimizations are shown. We obtained the shapes, which have notch around the cap. In such shapes, the notch partially reduces stiffness of the liner and prevents opening of crack. Optimal shapes for both cooling and pressure have similar notched shape and both of them can reduce the value of objective function. Then, the structure that has the notch is effective for prevent propagation of crack. However, because the value of optimal structure is more than 1.0, crack progress and the tank may be broken. It should be noted that the same concepts are seen in [10, 11]. In these concepts, structures have the part of low stiffness. This part can relax the thermal stress and reduce crack opening displacement. Thus these structures could reduce energy release rate (see Fig. 10).

Figure 9 Solution obtained by the optimization of liner thickness.

Figure 10 Comparison of mode I fracture energy release rate between initial model and result of liner thickness optimization.

5.2 Result of optimization for curved surface shape

Figure 11 shows the portion, which strongly affected the value of objective function in curved surface shape optimization. Figure 12 and 13 show comparison of initial model and optimal shape in ‘Cooling optimization’ and ‘Pressure optimization’. In the optimal shape for cooling, flexure deformation that was caused by thermal shrinkage, was suppressed near the cap during cooling. This structure is similar to notch-like structure in Fig. 9. On the other hand, the optimal shape for pressure can reduce the value of objective function by the deformation due to the pressure. Because of pressure, bending deformation occurs in this shape, and it closes the crack. Comparison between the results of ‘Cooling optimization’ and ‘Pressure optimization’ revealed that the energy release rate in ‘Pressure optimized’ shape is smaller than that in ‘Cooling optimized’ shape even in the cooling condition, although ‘Cooling optimized’ shape was calculated from the optimization of the cooling condition. In this case, ‘Pressure optimization’ effectively suppressed flexure deformation beside the cap and prevented crack propagation. Therefore ‘Cooling optimization’ was the local optimized solution. Above discussion concludes that the dome shape of ‘Pressure optimization’ is more suitable.

Figure 11 Solution obtained by the optimization of curved surface shapes.

Mode I fracture energy release rate (Cooling deformation)

0 1.1 kJ/mm²

(a) Initial model

(b) Cooling optimization

Figure 12 Comparison of mode I fracture energy release rate between initial model and optimal shape for cooling deformation.

Mode I fracture energy release rate (Pressure deformation)

0 2.2 kJ/mm²

(a) Initial model

(b) Pressure optimization

Figure 13 Comparison of mode I fracture energy release rate between initial model and optimal shape for pressure deformation.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted optimizations about CFRP cryogenic tank by genetic algorithm. We conducted four types of optimizations in this study, and all of the optimized shapes calculated by them could reduce the value of objective function. In the shape that includes the notch in the liner and the dome shape that was obtained from the optimization of curved surface shape, it is conceivable that the value of the objective function changed depend on the notch position. If we provide the notch in suitable position, it is possible to prevent propagation of crack.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Morino, T. Shimoda, T. Morimoto, T. Ishikawa and T. Aoki, *Applicability of CFRP materials to the cryogenic propellant tank for reusable launch vehicle*, Advanced Composite Materials, 2001, (Vol.10, pp.339-347)
- [2] K. Higuchi, S. Takeuchi, E. Sato, Y. Naruo, Y. Inatani, F. Namiki, K. Tanaka and Y. Watabe, *Development and flight test of metal-lined CFRP cryogenic tank for reusable rocket*, 2005, Acta Astronautica, (Vol.57, pp.432-437)
- [3] J. Schneider, M. Dyess, C. Hasting, J. Patterson, J. Noorda and T. DeLay, *Lightweight cryogenic composite over-wrapped pressure vessels (COPVs) for launch vehicle applications*, 48th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, 2007
- [4] Ronald Krueger, *Virtual crack closure technique: History, approach, and applications*, Applied Mechanics Reviews, (2004), Vol. 57, No. 2, pp. 109-143
- [5] A. Yoshimura, T. Takaki, Y. Noji, T. Yokozeki, T. Ogasawara and S. Ogihara, *Fracture toughness of CFRP adhesive bonded joints at cryogenic temperature*, Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology, 2012, (Vol.26, pp.1017-1031)
- [6] T. Aoki, T. Ishikawa, H. Kumazawa, Y. Morino, *Cryogenic mechanical properties of CF/polymer composites for tanks of reusable rockets*. Advanced Composite Materials, (2001). Vol. 10, No.4, pp. 349-356.
- [7] T. Yokozeki, T. Ogasawara, T. Aoki, T. Ishikawa, *Experimental evaluation of gas permeability through damaged composite laminates for cryogenic tank*. Composites Science and Technology, (2009). Vol. 69, No.9, pp. 1334-1340.
- [8] John A. Nairn, *Energy release rate analysis for adhesive and laminate double cantilever beam specimens emphasizing the effect of residual stresses*. International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives, (2000). Vol. 20, No.1, pp. 59-70.
- [9] Akinori Yoshimura, Tomohiro Takaki, Yohei Noji, Tomohiro Yokozeki, Toshio Ogasawara, Shinji Ogihara, *Fracture Toughness of CFRP Adhesive Bonded Joints at Cryogenic Temperature*. Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology, (2012). Vol. 26, No.7, pp. 1017-1031.
- [10] S. Takeuchi, E. Sato, J Onoda, Y. Arakawa and A. Miyahara, *Contribution of Reduction Method for Energy Release Rate of Adhesive Bonding Structure in Composite Tank around Mouthpiece*, Journal of the Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences, 2010, (Vol.58, pp. 302-307)
- [11] A. Yoshimura, T. Ogasawara and H. Suemasu, *Validation of thermal stress reduction design of CFRP cryogenic propellant tank by LN2 immersion test*, JAXA Research and Development Memorandum (in Japanese), 2013